

SafeMut (ctDNA, simulate then remove duplicates)

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Batch

- A 1
- B 2
- C 3
- D 4
- E 5
- F 6
- G 7
- H 8
- I 9
- J 10
- K 11
- L 12

Allele fraction type

- Reference truth
- Real variant
- Simulated variant

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